

ROLE OF RASHTRIYA KRISHI VIKAS YOJANA (RKVY) SCHEME IN PROMOTING AGRIPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract:

Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) encourages innovation and agri entrepreneurs through skill development and financial support. It will produce funds for supporting any projects as per their local needs, preferably for innovative activities in agriculture and allied sectors. The study was based on secondary data. The collected data were analysed using Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) to examine the status of the RKVY scheme. From the results of the study, it can be seen that under the RKVY scheme, 17,730 projects were approved at a cost of Rs. 1,25,818 crore in India. Among them, 1,065 approved projects at a cost of Rs. 7,063 crore were from Karnataka. This indicates that Karnataka's per cent share was 6 per cent for the approved projects. Hence, it can be observed that Government programmes were significantly impacting the increase of agriprenurship at all India level, but in Karnataka they were found to be less effective. So, there is a need for agri incubation centres in Karnataka to take some measures in order to increase the share of Karnataka in agriprenurship.

Key- Words: Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY), Agriprenurship, Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), Projects

Introduction:

Entrepreneurship development is an empowerment strategy to promote income generating enterprises that generate sufficient livelihood and economic sustenance for family income. While, agriculture development is a requirement for the success of our country, as it is the principal means of livelihood for the people. Hence, as a combination of both, the entrepreneurship applied in the field of agriculture and allied sectors would help in achieving socio-economic development of the country.

In this background, the Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) was initiated in 2007 as an umbrella scheme for ensuring holistic development of agriculture and allied sectors by allowing states to choose their own agriculture and allied sector development activities as per the district or state agriculture plan. Since 2015-16, the funding pattern of the scheme has been altered to a ratio of 60:40 between the central and state government, whereas it is 90:10 for the North Eastern and Himalayan states and 100 per cent for Union territories by central grant.

RKVY scheme incentivizes states to increase public investment in agriculture and allied sectors. Under RKVY, states have been provided flexibility and autonomy for selection, planning approval and execution of projects or programmes under the scheme as per their needs, priorities and agro-climatic requirements. The funds are released to the State governments or Union Territories on the basis of projects approved in the State Level Sanctioning Committee meeting (SLSC), which is headed by the Chief Secretary of the concerned state and is the empowered body to approve projects under the scheme. It is for the State government to further implement the scheme in the state as per its requirements in areas that require focused attention for increasing production and productivity in the state.

This scheme was updated as RKVY-Remunerative Approaches for Agriculture and Allied sector Rejuvenation (RAFTAAR) for three years *i.e.*, 2017-18 to 2019-20 with a financial allocation of Rs. 15,722 crore and broad objectives of making farming a remunerative economic activity through strengthening the farmer's effort, risk mitigation and promoting agribusiness entrepreneurship. Under this scheme, they provide grant-in-aid for, establishment of RKVY-RAFTAAR agribusiness incubators (Rs. 233 lakh); seed stage funding for start-ups as a grant-in-aid (up to Rs. 25 lakh); and agriprenurship orientation and idea or pre-seed stage funding (up to Rs. 5 lakh). In this backdrop, the present study aims at examining the status of Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) in promoting agriprenurship.

Materials And Methods:

The study was based on secondary data. The required data were collected from the published sources like Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) management information system (Anonymous, 2022) and analysed using Compound Annual Growth Rate technique.

Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) analysis

The analysis of growth rate is usually used in economic studies to find out the trend of a particular variable over a period of time. It clearly indicates the performance of the variables considered and hence it can be very well used for making interpretations and to evolve policy decisions. Compound Annual Growth Rate was evaluated to see the growth of approved projects under Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana in India from the year 2007-08 to 2021-22. The growth model used is specified as follows:

$$Y_t = A B^t V_t \dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

Y_t = Number of approved projects in the year t

A = Intercept indicating the Y in the base period (t = 0)

B = 1+g

t = time period

V_t = Random disturbance term

Equation (1) was converted into the logarithmic form as follows to make it in a linear form:

$$\ln Y_t = \ln A + t * \ln B + \ln V_t$$

This is of the following form,

$$Q_t = a + bt + U_t \dots\dots (2)$$

Where,

Q_t = ln Y

a = ln A

b = ln B

U_t = ln V_t

The values 'a' and 'b' were estimated by using Ordinary Least Squares estimation technique. Later, the original 'A' and 'B' parameters in equation (1) were obtained by taking antilogarithms of 'a' and 'b' values as;

A = Antilog (a)

B = Antilog (b)

Compound annual growth rate (%) was calculated as follows:

$$g = (B - 1) * 100$$

Results and Discussion**Status of Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY)****Status of ACABC scheme in India**

RKVY was established with the goal of encouraging states to develop more thorough plans for their agricultural sector, taking into account the agroclimatic conditions, natural issues and technology, fully integrating livestock, poultry and fisheries. The plans would then be implemented with convergence for the inclusive development of agriculture and related sectors. With this aim under RKVY, from the

year 2007-08 to 2022-23, 17,730 projects were approved at a cost of Rs. 1,25,818 crore, covering 21 different sectors related to agriculture and allied activities, as shown in the Table 1 and 2. Among them, 8,680 projects (48.96 %) were completed at a cost of Rs. 62,461 crore (49.79 %), 8,470 were ongoing projects (47.77 %) at a cost of Rs. 61,020 crore (48.50 %), 123 projects (0.69 %) were desanctioned at a cost of Rs. 450 crore (0.36 %) and remaining 457 projects (2.58 %) were abandoned at a cost of Rs. 1,710 crore (1.36 %).

Under RKVY, projects proposed by the agripreneurs would be approved if they had an innovative idea based on technology, service, business platforms, etc., for enhancing efficiency in agriculture and allied sectors. Additionally, the amount sanctioned for each project will vary depending on its weightage and requirements. As a result, the majority of the projects that were approved and completed were from the state of Kerala in terms of number (1386 and 1085, respectively). While in terms of cost, they were from the state of Jharkhand (Rs. 13636 crore and Rs. 12183 crore, respectively). Whereas, the maximum share of ongoing projects was from Andhra Pradesh in terms of number (769) and Maharashtra in terms of cost (Rs. 4812 crore). The highest number of projects were approved under horticulture in terms of number (2521), whereas in terms of cost, a large amount was approved under crop development (Rs. 37653 crore). It also revealed that, from 2007-08 to 2021-22, the total number of approved projects declined while costs climbed, indicating a higher proportion of amount was being spent on each project.

There is very little likelihood of expanding the area under cultivation due to rising population pressure on land. Therefore, it is highly desirable to boost crop productivity through the employment of appropriate technologies for creating better crop varieties and better cultivation techniques for lowering cultivation costs. The number and cost of approved projects increased in sectors like cooperatives and cooperation (CAGR of 6.62 % and 14.35 % respectively), crop development (CAGR of 3.37 % and 12.71 % respectively), research (CAGR of 6.53 % and 5.26 % respectively), sericulture (CAGR of 7.05 % and 16.25 % respectively) and others (CAGR of 12.86 % and 30.17 % respectively) (Table 3). This indicates that due to the growing importance of agricultural research and crop development, the scheme gave more attention to the development of these activities and that more innovative projects were proposed by beneficiaries related to these activities.

Share of Karnataka to India under RKVY

The year-wise percentage share of Karnataka to India under RKVY from 2007-08 to 2022-23 are depicted in Table 4. There is a greater opportunity and need to expand the agripreneurship orientation programme in Karnataka in order to encourage more innovative projects from agripreneurs. It is evidenced by the fact that Karnataka accounted for only a six per cent share with India in terms of

approved, completed and ongoing projects each and five per cent in terms of remaining projects. The highest percentage share was found in the years 2020–21 for the number of approved (13%) and ongoing projects (14%), 2017–18 for completed projects (11%) and 2014–15 for abandoned projects (29%). Kalamkar and Swain (2015) reported that Karnataka accounted for more than five per cent of total expenditures made under RKVY in India.

Conclusion:

The present study has revealed that under the RKVY scheme, 17,730 projects were approved at a cost of Rs. 1,25,818 crore in India. The number and cost of approved projects increased in sectors like cooperatives and cooperation (CAGR of 6.62 % and 14.35 % respectively), crop development (CAGR of 3.37 % and 12.71 % respectively), research (CAGR of 6.53 % and 5.26 % respectively), sericulture (CAGR of 7.05 % and 16.25 % respectively) and others. Among the total approved projects in India, 1,065 approved projects at a cost of Rs. 7,063 crore were from Karnataka. This indicates that Karnataka's per cent share was 6 per cent for the approved projects. Hence, from the study it can be suggested that Government programmes were significantly impacting the increase of agripreneurship at the national level, but that in Karnataka they were found to be less effective. So, there is a need for agri incubation centres in Karnataka to take some measures to increase the state's share of agripreneurship.

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Table 1: Year-wise status of Rastriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) in India from 2007-08 to 2022-23

(Rs. In crore)

Sl No.	Year	Approved projects		Completed projects				Ongoing projects				De sanctioned projects				Abandoned projects			
		No.	Cost	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%
1	2007-08	482	1476	439	91.08	1295	87.74	23	4.77	115	7.79	0	0.00	0	0.00	20	4.15	66	4.47
2	2008-09	867	3985	738	85.12	3175	79.67	87	10.03	703	17.64	0	0.00	0	0.00	42	4.84	108	2.71
3	2009-10	1178	4765	989	83.96	3410	71.56	131	11.12	1177	24.70	0	0.00	0	0.00	58	4.92	179	3.76
4	2010-11	1618	8399	1225	75.71	5290	62.98	311	19.22	2956	35.19	0	0.00	0	0.00	82	5.07	152	1.81
5	2011-12	1614	8809	996	61.71	4848	55.03	517	32.03	3549	40.29	0	0.00	0	0.00	101	6.26	411	4.67
6	2012-13	1820	12515	1084	59.56	5292	42.29	681	37.42	6840	54.65	0	0.00	0	0.00	55	3.02	383	3.06
7	2013-14	1508	21565	879	58.29	17227	79.88	584	38.73	4210	19.52	0	0.00	0	0.00	45	2.98	128	0.59
8	2014-15	2149	21936	1263	58.77	15348	69.97	838	38.99	6331	28.86	0	0.00	0	0.00	48	2.23	258	1.18
9	2015-16	1200	7041	294	24.50	1512	21.47	881	73.42	5437	77.22	22	1.83	83	1.18	3	0.25	9	0.13
10	2016-17	1228	8492	276	22.48	1834	21.60	911	74.19	6582	77.51	41	3.34	76	0.89	0	0.00	0	0.00
11	2017-18	1134	8347	195	17.20	1425	17.07	886	78.13	6660	79.79	51	4.50	248	2.97	2	0.18	15	0.18
12	2018-19	949	6073	114	12.01	927	15.26	829	87.36	5120	84.31	5	0.53	25	0.41	1	0.11	0.3	0.00
13	2019-20	822	4710	117	14.23	642	13.63	704	85.64	4063	86.26	1	0.12	5	0.11	0	0.00	0	0.00
14	2020-21	666	4737	49	7.36	300	6.33	615	92.34	4429	93.50	2	0.30	8	0.17	0	0.00	0	0.00
15	2021-22	419	2627	22	5.25	116	4.42	396	94.51	2507	95.43	1	0.24	5	0.19	0	0.00	0	0.00
16	2022-23	76	341	0	0.00	0	0.00	76	100.00	341	100.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
	Total	17730	125818	8680	48.96	62641	49.79	8470	47.77	61020	48.50	123	0.69	450	0.36	457	2.58	1710	1.36

Source: RKVY, MIS report

Table 2: State-wise status of Rastriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) in India as on September 2022

(Rs. In crore)

Sl No.	State	Approved projects				Completed projects				Ongoing projects				De sanctioned projects				Abandoned projects				
		No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	
1	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	10	0	28	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Andhra Pradesh	1020	6	6227	5	238	3	1359	2	769	9	4812	8	0	0	0	0	13	3	57	3	
3	Arunachal Pradesh	301	2	10062	8	145	2	9853	16	139	2	199	0	0	0	0	0	17	4	10	1	
4	Assam	522	3	3530	3	200	2	1185	2	312	4	2308	4	0	0	0	0	10	2	36	2	
5	Bihar	493	3	4617	4	260	3	3153	5	185	2	1158	2	0	0	0	0	48	11	306	18	
6	Chattisgarh	807	5	3519	3	468	5	1316	2	336	4	2201	4	0	0	0	0	3	1	3	0	
7	Goa	126	1	288	0	39	0	36	0	50	1	173	0	12	10	15	3	25	5	64	4	
8	Gujarat	747	4	6818	5	327	4	1986	3	385	5	4661	8	4	3	70	15	31	7	101	6	
9	Haryana	672	4	3973	3	192	2	1128	2	451	5	2813	5	0	0	0	0	29	6	32	2	
10	Himachal Pradesh	361	2	696	1	185	2	380	1	173	2	315	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	1	0	
11	Jammu and Kashmir	661	4	541	0	160	2	110	0	467	6	417	1	0	0	0	0	34	7	14	1	
12	Jharkhand	285	2	13636	11	98	1	12183	19	128	2	1273	2	0	0	0	0	59	13	181	11	
13	Karnataka	1065	6	7063	6	511	6	3704	6	529	6	3227	5	0	0	0	0	25	5	132	8	
14	Kerala	1386	8	2581	2	1085	13	1418	2	280	3	1092	2	0	0	0	0	21	5	71	4	
15	Madhya Pradesh	837	5	7963	6	432	5	4282	7	381	4	3507	6	0	0	0	0	24	5	174	10	
16	Maharashtra	554	3	10819	9	72	1	1538	2	481	6	9280	15	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	
17	Manipur	258	1	239	0	97	1	108	0	160	2	129	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	
18	Meghalaya	362	2	517	0	205	2	278	0	155	2	231	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	8	0	
19	Mizoram	593	3	447	0	451	5	392	1	142	2	55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
20	Nagaland	544	3	599	0	175	2	193	0	369	4	405	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
21	Orissa	851	5	6434	5	588	7	4349	7	211	2	1848	3	35	28	191	42	17	4	46	3	
22	Punjab	363	2	4088	3	87	1	468	1	276	3	3620	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
23	Rajasthan	719	4	6037	5	174	2	1238	2	526	6	4561	7	1	1	2	0	18	4	236	14	
24	Sikkim	59	0	74	0	36	0	39	0	23	0	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
25	Tamil Nadu	949	5	6307	5	778	9	5107	8	167	2	1189	2	0	0	0	0	4	1	11	1	
26	Telangana	478	3	2322	2	127	1	220	0	325	4	2033	3	20	16	47	10	6	1	22	1	
27	Tripura	409	2	887	1	263	3	475	1	78	1	314	1	37	30	46	10	31	7	52	3	
28	Uttar Pradesh	886	5	9180	7	213	2	2262	4	652	8	6830	11	0	0	0	0	21	5	87	5	
29	Uttarakhand	267	2	1150	1	132	2	300	0	134	2	849	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	
30	West Bengal	1145	6	5177	4	942	11	3581	6	176	2	1455	2	14	11	80	18	13	3	61	4	
	Total	17730	100	125821	100	8680	100	62641	100	8470	100	61020	100	123	100	450	100	457	100	1709	100	

Source: RKVY, MIS report

Table 3: Sector-wise approved projects under Rastriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) in India

(Rs. In crore)

SI No.	Year	2007-08				2022-23				Total				CAGR (%) (2007-08 to 2021-22)	
		No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	%	Cost	%	No.	Cost
1	Agricultural Mechanization	18	4	67	5	3	4	50	15	813	5	9714	8	-1.42	4.91*
2	Animal Husbandry	71	15	105	7	0	0	0	0	2475	14	10801	9	-8.18**	-0.42
3	Cooperatives and Cooperation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	305	2	2154	2	6.62*	14.35***
4	Crop Development	17	4	53	4	10	13	68	20	1454	8	37653	30	3.37	12.71
5	Dairy Development	35	7	57	4	1	1	3	1	711	4	3439	3	-6.84**	-3.70
6	Extension	28	6	85	6	3	4	14	4	756	4	4379	3	-5.52**	2.08
7	Fertilizers and INM	21	4	55	4	1	1	2	1	272	2	1277	1	-8.59***	-10.67**
8	Fisheries	70	15	64	4	0	0	0	0	1525	9	3519	3	-5.63**	-0.48
9	Horticulture	62	13	96	6	7	9	20	6	2521	14	14455	11	-1.52	5.64
10	Information Technology	4	1	13	1	1	1	2	0	82	0	450	0	-5.62	-6.73
11	Innovative programmes /Training/Capacity building/ Others	6	1	97	7	1	1	0	0	623	4	4208	3	1.47	-5.12**
12	Integrated Pest management	8	2	6	0	2	3	8	2	317	2	1151	1	-0.64	5.91
13	Marketing and Post-harvest management	28	6	100	7	33	43	109	32	752	4	5010	4	-8.34**	-2.43
14	Micro/Minor irrigation	17	4	268	18	0	0	0	0	665	4	8418	7	-9.71**	-14.34***
15	Natural Resource Management	27	6	124	8	3	4	13	4	729	4	5389	4	-3.23	-2.04
16	Non-Farm activities	12	2	5	0	0	0	0	0	234	1	623	0	-10.88**	-6.32
17	Organic farming/Bio fertilizer	19	4	65	4	0	0	0	0	401	2	1904	2	-9.06**	-1.54*
18	Research (Agri/Horti/Animal Husbandry, etc.,)	13	3	59	4	4	5	19	6	1630	9	3024	2	6.53*	5.26*
19	Seed	23	5	157	11	3	4	23	7	913	5	6968	6	-2.45	-0.51
20	Sericulture	3	1	0	0	4	5	10	3	423	2	809	1	7.05*	16.25*
21	Others	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	129	1	476	0	12.86	30.17**
	Total	482	100	1476	100	76	100	341	100	17730	100	125820	100	-3.01**	0.59*

Source: RKVY, MIS report

Table 4: Percentage share of approved projects in Karnataka under Rastriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) in India from 2007-08 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Year	No. of approved Projects			No. of completed Projects			No. of ongoing Projects			No. of abandoned projects		
		India	Karnataka	% of Karnataka	India	Karnataka	% of Karnataka	India	Karnataka	% of Karnataka	India	Karnataka	% of Karnataka
1	2007-08	482	9	2	439	8	2	23	1	4	20	0	0
2	2008-09	867	24	3	738	22	3	87	1	1	42	1	2
3	2009-10	1178	51	4	989	50	5	131	1	1	58	0	0
4	2010-11	1618	59	4	1225	54	4	311	5	2	82	0	0
5	2011-12	1614	67	4	996	59	6	517	8	2	101	0	0
6	2012-13	1820	89	5	1084	70	6	681	15	2	55	4	7
7	2013-14	1508	107	7	879	83	9	584	18	3	45	6	13
8	2014-15	2149	131	6	1263	98	8	838	19	2	48	14	29
9	2015-16	1200	68	6	294	12	4	881	56	6	3	0	0
10	2016-17	1228	84	7	276	14	5	911	70	8	0	0	0
11	2017-18	1134	92	8	195	22	11	886	70	8	2	0	0
12	2018-19	949	51	5	114	8	7	829	43	5	1	0	0
13	2019-20	822	90	11	117	10	9	704	80	11	0	0	0
14	2020-21	666	89	13	49	1	2	615	88	14	0	0	0
15	2021-22	419	52	12	22	0	0	396	52	13	0	0	0
16	2022-23	76	2	3	0	0	0	76	2	3	0	0	0
	Total	17730	1065	6	8680	511	6	8470	529	6	457	25	5

Source: RKVY, MIS report